

EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE ON SORBENTS

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ABSTRACT

The information presented in this work is of great practical importance. With its help, the production process of sorbents for wastewater treatment becomes easier and does not require a lot of time, thereby helping the ecological development of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The experiments carried out during this work allow us to open the prospects of using natural clay materials, thiourea and polyethyleneimine for efficient and ash treatment of waste water of industrial enterprises.

Key words: metallurgy, mechanical engineering, metal, waste water, copper, cadmium, lead, mercury, zinc, ion.

Introduction. In the last 20 years, researchers have been increasingly interested in developing new methods and materials for the extraction of hazardous pollutants from wastewater. Heavy metal pollution is the most common problem in the aquatic environment due to its persistence and toxicity. High consumption of heavy metals in addition to sodium causes various diseases: nausea, abdominal pain, gastrointestinal disorders, neurological dysfunction, hemolysis, liver and kidney damage. Metallurgy, machine-building, and metal processing industry are the main sources of environmental pollution with heavy metal ions, their wastewater contains ions of copper, cadmium, lead, mercury, zinc, and others. The problem of cleaning surface and wastewater from heavy metals is the main problem of protection of the external environment, since HM causes great damage to the biosphere.

In addition, this research aims to develop cost-effective technologies for the separation of metal ions from wastewater. The most effective method of sorption cleaning is considered, as well as the most effective sorbents, natural mud materials are selected, their modification with various substances increases their sorption properties.

The process of sorption of cadmium and lead ions using modified sorbent was studied at three temperatures: 277 K, 298 K and 308 K.

Studying the effect of temperature allows to calculate the sorption rate

constants, sorption rate and activation energy of the process, the results of which are presented in Figures 1 and 2 and Table 1.

Fig. 1 Time dependence of the extraction rate of $-Cd^{2+}$ ions by BG+PEI sorbent at different temperatures ($pH = 6$, $C_{isx} = 100$ mkg/ml, $C_{pzi} = 0,1\%$).

Time dependence of Risunok 2- $P2^{2+}$ ion extraction rate of BG+PEI sorbent at different temperatures. ($pH = 6$, $C_{isx} = 100$ mkg/ml, $C_{pzi} = 0,1\%$).

The data presented in Figures 1 and 2 show that the temperature change has little effect on the ion sorption process. This mechanism of chemisorption is the formation of a complex between the sorbent and the sorbate shows.

Table 1 - kinetic characteristics of sorption of $-Cd^{2+}$ and Pb^{2+} ions with modified bentonite.

Metal ion	T, K	K, min^{-1}	w, mkg/ml*min	E_a , kJ/mol
Cd^{2+}	277	$0,062 \pm 0,002$	1,22	5,285
	298	$0,079 \pm 0,004$	1,38	
	308	$0,082 \pm 0,001$	1,63	
Pb^{2+}	277	$0,041 \pm 0,001$	0,47	12,795
	298	$0,047 \pm 0,002$	1,94	
	308	$0,064 \pm 0,003$	2,22	

The data in Table 1 show that the rate constants of the process increase with increasing temperature. It is active due to the increase in the rate of sorption, the extimol, the increase in the activity of TM ions in the solution, as well as the disruption of some internal bonds on the surface of the sorbent.

The most important characteristics of adsorption isotherms at different temperatures were calculated to determine thermodynamic properties such as equilibrium constants, enthalpy, entropy and Gibbs energy.

According to Table 2, the optimum temperature is 308 K for cadmium ions and 298 K for lead ions, where the equilibrium constants and maximum adsorption values are maximum. The data in the table show that the correlation coefficients for cadmium ion and lead are close to unity according to the Langmuir theory for all temperatures.

2 tables - Characteristics of adsorption isotherms of metal ions with modified sorbent at different temperatures.

Metal ion	Langmuir theory				Freundlich theory		
	T,K	K, l/mg	A _∞ , mg/l	R ²	β	1/n	R ²
Cd ²⁺	277	0,2682	15,6	0,965	5,05	4,2	0,836
	298	0,1422	15,8	0,973	5,82	4,8	0,847
	308	0,1854	17,8	0,998	4,78	3,23	0,968
Pb ²⁺	277	0,460	5,8	0,923	2,26	0,51	0,888
	298	0,1082	11,6	0,941	1,48	0,73	0,783
	308	0,92	6,7	0,867	3,45	0,98	0,640

Of metal ion adsorption onto BG+PEI sorbent effect explanation for thermodynamic indicators counting from: Gibbs free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS).

Positive values of Gibbs free energy indicate that the sorption of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions on the surface of the sorbent is not simultaneous.

A positive entropy value for lead ion indicates an increase in randomness at the solid/liquid interface during adsorption. A negative value of the entropy change indicates a decrease in randomness at the solid/liquid interface during sorption.

Based on the results of the study of the effect of various factors on the sorption of Cd²⁺ and Pb²⁺ ions, the optimal values of the sorbent were determined: the optimal concentration of modified PEI in the sorbent was 0.1% at T=298 K, and the mass of the sorbent was equal to 6 for cadmium and lead in 100 ml solution for 1 gram.

REFERENCES

1. E.Egamberdiev, S. Turabdjanov, D. Mirzaeva, Kh. Khaydullaev, U. Sharipova, A. Shokhakimova, and O. Bakhtiyorov.: Effect of chitosan substance on the mechanical properties of paper obtained on the basis of flax cellulose. E3S Web of Conferences 371, 01045 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202337101045>
2. Egamberdiev E.; Ergashev Y.; Turabdjanov S.; Abdumavlyanova M.; Makhkamov A.; Rashidov, Sh.; Karimov, Sh.: Effect of chitosan on the surface

properties of cellulose-based paper obtained from the flax plant. E3S Web of Conferences 371, 01010 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202337101010>

3. Ergashev Y.; Egamberdiev E.; Mirkhodjaeva D.; Akmalova G.; Umarova M.; Kholdarov R.: Obtaining a filter material used in gas and air purification. E3S Web of Conferences 371, 01012 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202337101012>

4. Igamqulova N.; Mengliev, Sh.; Egamberdiev E.: Reduction of waste disposed to the environment through recycling of unused methyldiethanolamine. E3S Web of Conferences 371, 01049 (2023) <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202337101049>

5. Arslanov, Sh.; Turabdjanov S.; Azimova, Sh.; Azimov D.; Sultankhojaeva N.; Egamberdiev E.: Physico-chemical properties and research of acids contained in oils of Uzbekistan. E3S Web of Conferences, 2023, 371, 01021, DOI 10.1051/e3sconf/202337101021

6. Egamberdiev E.; Turabdjanov S.; Akmalova G.; Mukhtarova N.; Ayubova I.; Mirzakhmedova M.; Rakhmonberdiev G.: Obtaining paper from composition of different fibers and its analysis. E3S Web of Conferences, 2023, 371, 01004, DOI 10.1051/e3sconf/202337101004

7. Ergashev Y.; Egamberdiev E.; Turabdzhanov S.; Akmalova G.; Isanova R.; Rashidov R.; Sobitov O.: Obtaining filter material from natural fiber composition and areas of its use. E3S Web of Conferences, 2023, 371, 01047, DOI 10.1051/e3sconf/202337101047

8. Egamberdiev E.; Makhkamov A.; Rakhimjonov B.; Khusanov D.; Akmalova G.; Mirzakhmedova M.; Rahmonberdiev G. Effectiveness of cleaning of sunflower oil with filter material made from composition of organic and inorganic fibers. 3rd International Conference on Energetics, Civil and Agricultural Engineering, ICECAE 2022Virtual, Online13 October 2022до 16 October 2022Код 187394, DOI 10.1088/1755-1315/1142/1/012050

9. Egamberdiev E.; Akmalova G.; Rahmonberdiev G. Obtaining paper products from cellulose-containing plants and researching its field of application. 3rd International Conference on Energetics, Civil and Agricultural Engineering, ICECAE 2022Virtual, Online13 October 2022до 16 October 2022Код 187394, DOI 10.1088/1755-1315/1142/1/012054